

Corrosion inhibition of copper by natural occurring plant *Acacia senegal*

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Abstract : The alcoholic extract of leaves, stem bark and gum from the *Acacia senegal* is tested for their effectiveness to combat corrosion of copper in molar hydrochloric acid by the mass loss method and thermometric method. It was found that the presence of the extracts reduce the corrosion rate of copper in acid solution. The inhibition efficiency increases as the extract concentration is increased. The adsorption of these natural products on the metal surface from the acid has been found to obey Langmuir adsorption isotherm. The gum extract of *Acacia senegal* shows maximum corrosion inhibition efficiency in the acid solution compare to leaves and stem bark extracts. The acacia extract provides a good protection to copper against corrosion.

Keywords : Mass loss, degradation, Mylius thermometric method, *Acacia senegal*, acid.

Introduction

Corrosion is an irreversible interfacial reaction of a material with its environment which results in consumption of the material or in dissolution into the material of a component of the environment. Metallic corrosion is a very common but serious problem causing considerable revenue loss throughout the world. Mitigation of corrosion requires the application of various engineering techniques and scientific knowledge on the role of the alloying element in the reduction of corrosion losses and application of the film forming inhibitors are well known¹.

The recent trend is towards environment-friendly inhibitors. Many current corrosion control methods use coating and conversion layers which contain toxic and environmentally hazardous material. There is a great need to find a non toxic replacement that is compatible with current industrial technologies. Well known as non toxic compound and due to their availability and relatively low cost, naturally substances find various applications in many fields. It has been show that natural product of plant origin contain different organic compound e.g. alkaloids, tannis, pigments, organic and amino acid and most are known to have inhibition action²⁻⁹. Numerous naturally occurring substances such as *Prosopis juliflora*¹⁰, *Ficus religiosa*¹¹, *Prosopis cineraria*¹², *Artocarpus heterophyllus*¹³, *Datura stramonium*¹⁴, *Ficus virens*¹⁵,

*Capparis deciduas*¹⁶ and *Lawsonia* extract¹⁷ have been evaluated as potential corrosion inhibitors. In the present work, an attempt has been made to study the influence of varying concentration of constituents and substitute extracts of *Acacia senegal* as probable acid corrosion inhibitor in hydrochloric acid in copper.

Acacia senegal is commonly used in the India system of medicines. The recent discovery show that plant extract of *Acacia senegal* (gum acacia) show antioxidant¹⁸ and antimicrobial activity¹⁹. It is used in antitussive, astringent, catarrh, colds, cough, diarrhea dysentery expectorant gonorrhoea, hemorrhage, sore throat, typhoid, urinary tract²⁰. Acacia seeds are often used for food and variety of other products.

Gum acacia contains neutral sugar (rhamnose, arbinose and galactose), acids (glucuronic acid and 4-methoxy glucuronic acid), calcium, magnesium, potassium and sodium. Its back bone chain consists of D-galactose unit and its side chain is composed of D-glucuronic acid units with 1-rhamnose 1-arabinose as ends units. The molecular weight has been reported to be between 200000 to 300000 and as high as 600000²¹. Leaves contain 10–13% digestible protein 0.12–0.14% phosphorus. The alkaloids found in *Acacia senegal* include less than 0.1% dimethyltryptamine (DMT) in leaf and N-methyltryptamine (NMT) in plants part²². Acacia seeds are highly nutritious and

contain 26% protein, 26% available carbohydrate, 32% fiber and 9% fat²³. Gum acacia contains alkaloid atropine (Fig. 1) and ascorbic acid probable has been found to be effective for inhibition of copper in acid media.

Fig. 1. Atropine.

Fig. 2. Ascorbic acid.

Results and discussion

Effect of inhibitor concentration :

The inhibition efficiency (IE) calculated from the mass loss measurement for different concentration of hydrochloric acid. The result show (Tables 1–4) that the efficiency increases with the inhibition concentration of plant extract from 0.12 to 0.60% in 0.1 N hydrochloric acid maximum inhibition efficiency is 88.81% for 0.60% concentration. The similar trend is found for 0.2 N to 1 N hydrochloric solution.

Effect of concentration of acid solution :

It is found that the leaves, bark and gum extracts for 0.1 N HCl acid have a good property to inhibit the corrosion of copper. It is observe that the inhibition efficiency decreases with increases acid concentration. *Acacia senegal* leaves show minimum 63.05% inhibition efficiency and maximum 85.42% efficiencies for 0.1 N hydrochloric acid solution but 1 N hydrochloric acid solution show minimum 56.41% efficiency and maximum 78.45% efficiency for copper.

The variation of reaction number with inhibitor concentration, presented graphically in Figs. 5–8, show reaction number decreases with increasing inhibitors concentration.

Kinetic parameter :

From Tables 1–4, the rate constant at 298 K show a general decrease with increases inhibitor concentration, inhibitor efficiency, half life of the metal-corrodant-inhibitor system. Similar trend in kinetic data has been reported by several investigators and indicate that a good inhibitor is one that is able to increase the time of conversion of metals to corrosion products. Tables show increases in half life when inhibitors are present, which further support the assertion that the natural products are corrosion inhibitors for copper in HCl solution.

Adsorption plays an important role in the inhibition of metallic corrosion by inhibitors. Many investigators have used the Langmuir adsorption isotherm to study inhibitors characteristics²⁴ assuming that the inhibitors adsorbed

Table 1. Effect of extract of different parts of plants *Acacia senegal* on mass loss data for corrosion of copper in 0.1 N HCl at 25 ± 0.1 °C

Inhibitor concentration	Mass loss (mg)	Inhibition efficiency (η%)	Surface coverage (θ)	Effective area of specimen : 7.50 cm ² , immersion time : 48 h			
				Corrosion rate	Corrosion current	Rate constant	Half life
Uninhibited	29.5	0.00	0.0000	0.80	2846750	0.0005	1491.76
Leaf							
0.12	10.9	63.05	0.6305	0.30	1051850	0.0002	4065.84
0.24	8.8	70.17	0.7017	0.24	849200	0.0001	5040.08
0.36	7.6	74.24	0.7424	0.21	733400	0.0001	5838.51
0.48	5.8	80.34	0.8034	0.16	559700	0.0001	7655.64
0.60	4.3	85.42	0.8542	0.12	4149501	0.0001	10332.02

Table-1 (contd.)

Bark							
0.12	9.3	68.47	0.6847	0.25	897450	0.0001	4768.21
0.24	7.8	73.56	0.7356	0.21	752700	0.0001	5688.38
0.36	6.3	78.64	0.7864	0.17	607950	0.0001	7046.73
0.48	5.9	80.00	0.8000	0.16	569350	0.0001	7525.60
0.60	3.3	88.81	0.8881	0.09	318450	0.0001	13467.97
Gum							
0.12	8.8	70.17	0.7017	0.24	849200	0.0001	5040.08
0.24	6.5	77.97	0.7797	0.18	627250	0.0001	6829.39
0.36	5.9	80.00	0.8000	0.16	569350	0.0001	7525.60
0.48	4.6	84.41	0.8441	0.12	443900	0.0001	9657.10
0.60	3.4	88.47	0.8847	0.09	328100	0.0001	13071.37

Table 2. Effect of extract of different parts of plants *Acacia senegal* on mass loss data for corrosion of copper in 0.2 N HCl at 25 ± 0.1 °C

Effective area of specimen : 7.50 cm ² , immersion time : 48 h							
Inhibitor concentration	Mass loss (mg)	Inhibition efficiency (η%)	Surface coverage (θ)	Corrosion rate	Corrosion current	Rate constant	Half life
Uninhibited	49.7	0.00	0.0000	1.35	4796050	0.0008	878.62
Leaf							
0.12	19.9	59.96	0.5996	0.54	1920350	0.0003	2219.47
0.24	15.8	68.21	0.6821	0.43	1524700	0.0002	2799.74
0.36	14.8	70.22	0.7022	0.40	1428200	0.0002	2990.04
0.48	10.8	78.27	0.7827	0.29	1042200	0.0002	4103.65
0.60	7.8	84.31	0.8431	0.21	752700	0.0001	5688.38
Bark							
0.12	17	65.79	0.6579	0.46	1640500	0.0003	2600.94
0.24	14.5	70.82	0.7082	0.39	1399250	0.0002	3052.25
0.36	12.7	74.45	0.7445	0.34	1225550	0.0002	3487.22
0.48	11.1	77.67	0.7767	0.30	1071150	0.0002	3992.29
0.60	9.3	81.29	0.8129	0.25	897450	0.0001	4768.21
Gum							
0.12	15.9	68.01	0.6801	0.43	1534350	0.0002	2782.03
0.24	12.5	74.85	0.7485	0.34	1206250	0.0002	3543.28
0.36	11.5	76.86	0.7686	0.31	1109750	0.0002	3852.84
0.48	9.5	80.89	0.8089	0.26	916750	0.0001	4667.48
0.60	7.8	84.31	0.8431	0.21	752700	0.0001	5688.38

Table 3. Effect of extract of different parts of plants *Acacia senegal* on mass loss data for corrosion of copper in 0.5 N HCl at 25 ± 0.1 °C

Effective area of specimen : 7.50 cm ² , immersion time : 48 h							
Inhibitor concentration	Mass loss (mg)	Inhibition efficiency (η%)	Surface coverage (θ)	Corrosion rate	Corrosion current	Rate constant	Half life
Uninhibited	112.1	0.00	0.0000	3.04	10817650	0.0018	380.09
Leaf							
0.12	45.95	59.01	0.5901	1.25	4434175	0.0007	951.70

Table-3 (contd.)

0.24	38.99	65.22	0.6522	1.06	3762535	0.0006	1124.59
0.36	35.58	68.26	0.6826	0.97	3433470	0.0006	1233.98
0.48	27.31	75.64	0.7564	0.74	2635415	0.0004	1612.72
0.60	19.26	82.82	0.8282	0.52	1858590	0.0003	2293.78
Bark							
0.12	44.8	60.04	0.6004	1.22	4323200	0.0007	976.56
0.24	38.4	65.74	0.6574	1.04	3705600	0.0006	1142.12
0.36	34.7	69.05	0.6905	0.94	3348550	0.0005	1265.70
0.48	28.9	74.22	0.7422	0.78	2788850	0.0005	1523.08
0.60	22.4	80.02	0.8002	0.61	2161600	0.0004	1969.90
Gum							
0.12	38.4	65.74	0.6574	1.04	3705600	0.0006	1142.12
0.24	32.6	70.92	0.7092	0.89	3145900	0.0005	1348.31
0.36	28.4	74.67	0.7467	0.77	2740600	0.0004	1550.19
0.48	24.8	77.88	0.7788	0.67	2393200	0.0004	1777.64
0.60	21.7	80.64	0.8064	0.59	2094050	0.0003	2033.98

Table 4. Effect of extract of different parts of plants *Acacia senegal* on mass loss data for corrosion of copper in 1 N HCl at 25 ± 0.1 °C

Effective area of specimen : 7.50 cm ² , immersion time : 48 h							
Inhibitor concentration	Mass loss (mg)	Inhibition efficiency (η%)	Surface coverage (θ)	Corrosion rate	Corrosion current	Rate constant	Half life
Uninhibited	124.8	0.00	0.0000	3.39	12043200	0.0020	339.66
Leaf							
0.12	54.4	56.41	0.5641	1.48	5249600	0.0009	801.26
0.24	49.8	60.10	0.6010	1.35	4805700	0.0008	876.82
0.36	42.8	65.71	0.6571	1.16	4130200	0.0007	1022.98
0.48	37.6	69.87	0.6987	1.02	3628400	0.0006	1166.78
0.60	26.9	78.45	0.7845	0.73	2595850	0.0004	1637.56
Bark							
0.12	53.8	56.89	0.5689	1.46	5191700	0.0009	810.38
0.24	49.9	60.02	0.6002	1.36	4815350	0.0008	875.03
0.36	46.3	62.90	0.6290	1.26	4467950	0.0007	944.38
0.48	36.2	70.99	0.7099	0.98	3493300	0.0006	1212.56
0.60	27.9	77.64	0.7764	0.76	2692350	0.0004	1578.27
Gum							
0.12	49.8	60.10	0.6010	1.35	4805700	0.0008	876.82
0.24	41.6	66.67	0.6667	1.13	4014400	0.0007	1052.91
0.36	36	71.15	0.7115	0.98	3474000	0.0006	1219.31
0.48	33.2	73.40	0.7340	0.90	3203800	0.0005	1323.64
0.60	25.7	79.81	0.7981	0.68	2431800	0.0004	1749.11

on the metal surface decreases the surface area available for the cathodic and anodic reactions to takes place.

Langmuir adsorption isotherm,

$$\log [\theta/1 - \theta] = \log A + \log C - (\theta/2.3RT)$$

Should give a straight line of unit gradient for the plot of $\log [\theta/1 - \theta]$ versus $\log C$ where θ is surface coverage, A

Fig. 3. Langmuir adsorption isotherm of senegal extract for copper in 0.5 N hydrochloric acid with inhibitor concentration

Fig. 4. Langmuir adsorption isotherm of senegal extract for copper in 1 N hydrochloric acid with inhibitor concentration

Fig. 5. Variation of reaction number vs concentration with all three inhibitors in 2 N hydrochloric acid solution in copper

Fig. 6. Variation of reaction number vs concentration with all three inhibitors in 3 N hydrochloric acid solution in copper

Fig. 7. Variation of reaction number vs concentration with all three inhibitors in 4 N hydrochloric acid solution in copper

Fig. 8. Variation of reaction number vs concentration with all three inhibitors in 5 N hydrochloric acid solution in copper

is a temperature independent constant and C is a concentration of the inhibitor. The corresponding plot (Figs 3 and 4) is linear but the gradients are not equal to unity as would be expected for the Langmuir adsorption isotherm equation. This deviation from the unity may be explained on the basis of the interaction among the adsorbed species on the metal surface.

Generally, the adsorption of organic molecules on metallic surfaces involves oxygen, nitrogen and sulphur atoms. In the case of plant extract of *Acacia senegal*, hydroxyl group of alkaloids, nitrogen of alkaloid and oxygen atom may be responsible for the adsorption

Organic inhibitor have active portions which are generally large C-H chains or rings with positively charged amine nitrogen groups at one end. In acids and water, the terminal primary secondary and tertiary amine groups take additional hydrogen that gives them a net positive charge. The polar amine group is adsorbed on the metal and the hydrocarbon portion forms an oily water repellent surface film. The molecular shape (dissymmetry) helps these materials act as surfactants and can stabilize emul-

sions of oil and water. Organic corrosion inhibitors^{25,26} may function by (1) chemisorptions of the molecule on a metallic surface, (2) complexation of the molecule with the metal ion, which remains in a solid state, (3) neutralizing the corrodant and (4) adsorbing the corrodant. They offered large coverage due to the long hydrocarbon chain and by the presence of OH groups. Being hydrophilic in nature, the OH groups' counters act the effects of chain length and ensure higher solubilities. Naturally occurring polymers such as starch, gum tragacanth, carboxy methyl-cellulose, alings tannis, lignosulphonates and gelatin were first used for scale control. They modify the crystal size and dispersants of micro crystallites^{27,28}. The process may block active sides, hence may decrease the corrosion rate. The OH⁻ group present in bark sterols exerts a positive inductive effect, which increases the electron density at the nitrogen atom of protein. This explains the higher inhibition efficiencies displayed by gum extract for 0.60% concentration.

Experimental

Rectangular specimen of metal of size $1.5 \times 2.5 \times 0.025$ cm were so cut from a sheet having a small hole of 2 mm diameter near the upper edge were employed for the determination of corrosion rate. To clean the specimens were abraded with various grades of wax coated emery paper (1/0, 2/0, 3/0, 4/0) and successively washed with benzene and soap and distilled water and finally with acetone then dried and weight. The metal coupons were then suspended with the help of glass hooks in borosil beakers containing 50 ml of corrosive electrolyte for complete immersion test. The solution of 0.1 N, 0.2 N, 0.5 N, 1 N to 5 N hydrochloric acid were prepared using doubly distilled water.

The senegal extract was obtained by dried the parts of plants, then finely powdered and extracted with boiling methanol. The solvent is distilled off, and residue treated with inorganic acid. Where the base is extracted as their soluble salt. The free bases are liberated by the addition of any base and extracted with various solvent e.g. ether, chloroform, etc. The mixture of base thus obtained is separated by various methods into the individual compound²⁹.

Mass loss method : The metal coupons were then suspended with the help of glass hooks in borosil beakers

containing 50 ml of corrosive electrolyte for complete immersion test at 298 ± 1 K. The duration of immersion time is 48 h and is indicated in respective Tables. After the test, specimens were cleaned with a saturated solution of ammonium acetate³⁰. Corrosion rate (mm py), inhibition efficiency ($\eta\%$) and rate constant were calculated from this mass loss data.

The inhibitor efficiency ($\eta\%$) is calculated as³¹,

$$\eta\% = 100(\Delta Mu - \Delta Mi/\Delta Mu)$$

where the ΔMu is the mass loss of metal in uninhibited acid and ΔMi is mass loss of metal in inhibited solution.

The degree of surface coverage (θ) can be calculated as³²,

$$\theta = \frac{\Delta Mu - \Delta Mi}{\Delta Mu}$$

where θ is the surface coverage and ΔMu and ΔMi are the mass loss of the metal in uninhibited acid and inhibited solution respectively.

The corrosion rate (mm year⁻¹) it can be obtained by the following equation³³,

$$\text{Corrosion rate (mm year}^{-1}\text{)} = \frac{\text{mass loss} \times 87.6}{\text{Area} \times \text{time} \times \text{density}}$$

where mass loss in mg, area is in cm² of metal surface exposed, the time is expressed in hours and metal density is expressed in g/cm³ and 87.6 is the conversion factor.

The corrosion current (i) can be calculated as³⁴,

$$\text{Corrosion current (}i\text{)} = \text{Corrosion rate} \times F/n$$

where F is faraday (96500) and n is number of electron.

The inhibitive action and the compound will also be investigated by using mylius thermometric method. This involved the immersion of single specimens ($2.5 \times 1.5 \times 0.025$ cm) in a reaction chamber containing 50 ml of solution at initial temperature 298 ± 0.1 K. Temperature changes were measured at intervals of 5 min using thermometer with a precision of 0.01 K. The temperature increased slowly at first then rapidly and attained a maximum value before falling.

The minimum temperature was recorded the percentage inhibition efficiencies in this case were calculated³⁵,

$$\eta = 100 (RN_{\text{free}} - RN_i)/RN_{\text{free}}$$

where RN_i and RN_{free} are the reaction numbers in the presence and absence of inhibitor respectively and RN ($K \text{ min}^{-1}$) is defined as

$$RN = (Tm - To)/t$$

where Tm and To are the maximum and initial temperature respectively and t is the time required to reach the maximum temperature in minutes

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